

Anatomical Variations of Koerner's Septum: A Single-Center Computed Tomography Study

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Introduction

Koerner's septum (KS) is a bony plate located at the junction of the petrous and squamous parts of the temporal bone. The reported prevalence of KS has varied between studies. KS variations are associated with various pathologies and pose difficulties during surgeries. The study aims to determine the KS frequency in Omani patients and analyze its association with sex and side.

Materials and Methods

The present study investigated the KS topography in 344 computed tomography (CT) scans of normal temporal bones of adult Omani patients at Sultan Qaboos University Hospital. The presence of KS and its parts (complete or incomplete), as well as its thickness at three anatomical landmarks, were recorded. Additionally, sex and laterality differences in KS parameters were analyzed using a Chi-square test.

Results

The overall frequency of KS among Omani subjects was 39.5%. Complete KS was observed in only 14% of cases. The thickness of KS was 0.78 ± 0.21 mm, 0.93 ± 0.28 mm, and 0.78 ± 0.21 mm at the head of the malleus (HM), the superior semicircular canal (SSC), and the tympanic sinus (TS), respectively ($p < 0.01$). KS was most frequently identified at the level of HM (64.7%), followed by SSC (57.4%), and less frequently at the level of TS (49.3%). KS frequency was similar between males and females (41.9% vs 37.3%), with statistically insignificant difference ($p = 0.38$). No side differences were observed concerning KS frequency ($p = 0.955$).

Conclusion

The frequency of Koerner's septum in Omani subjects was within the range reported in previous studies. It is incomplete in most cases and constantly present at the level of HM. Its thickness is greater at the level of SSC.

Keywords

Ear surgery; Koerner's septum; Mastoid process; Middle ear; Temporal bone.